

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF A COMPOSITE BEAM SUB-STRUCTURAL TEST SPECIMEN

Alex Quinlan, Department of Civil Engineering, Technical University of Denmark

Multi-Scale Motivation

The Villum Center for Advanced Structural and Material Testing (CASMaT) is taking a multi-scale approach to studying fatigue damage in composites. Multi-scale modelling can illuminate the path from micro-mechanics to structural performance, but it needs to be partnered with experiments to step successfully through the length-scales. The multi-scale framework in development can provide designers with a tool to optimize experimental testing, thus lowering the time and cost for new product introduction. In this project, the modelling and testing at the micro-scale, macro-scale, and sub-structural scale have been divided between three PhD students. This poster presents the **sub-structural scale** PhD work.

Project Goal: To predict the evolution of *off-axis matrix crack density* in a structure using a micro-mechanics based finite element model

First Step: Before a complex phenomenon like damage can be successfully modeled, the elastic response of the sub-structure needs to be validated. If the numerical model cannot predict the strains and displacement of the specimen, then it will not be able to predict the crack density evolution. The numerical predictions are compared to strain and displacement measurements acquired through digital image correlation (DIC) and digital image displacement tracking.

Experimental Set-up

Thin-Wall Beam Specimen

Length: 1050 mm
Cross Section: 200x140 mm
Wall Thickness: Variable (4-26 mm)
Material: E-glass / Epoxy
Wall Layup: $[0^\circ/-60^\circ/0^\circ/60^\circ]_s$
Reinforcement: $[0^\circ_n]$

Test Frame

Steel beams on *strong-floor*
Bolted steel interfaces
50 kN Vertical Actuator
25 kN Horizontal Actuator (x2)
In-plane loading (X, Y, Rotation Z)

Finite Element Modelling

Results, Discussion, and Future Work

Can the model predict how the beam deflects upward under load? The linear FE model matches the DIC results. The non-linear model over-estimates the displacement

Can the model predict the strain field on the bottom surface? The non-linear model over-estimates the strains

Note: The DIC data has been smoothed with an averaging filter of window size 50

Has the model been experimentally validated? No, not yet

Possible Causes of Discrepancies

1. Finite element model formulation
2. Erroneous DIC measurements
3. Manufacturing-based deviations from design